

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK AT SCHOOL

Shamsiddinova Saodat

Student of the Bukhara State

Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: The article discusses the features of organizing and conducting independent work as one of the ways to stimulate active learning activities of students. The author concludes that the ability to work independently contributes to the formation of students' desire to be self-confident, independent, educated and creative in thinking.

Keywords: lesson, independent work, educational process, problem-searching activity, educational tasks, means of stimulation.

In the modern world, where life requires high standards, and the organization of education and upbringing is under constant attention, there is a need for new, more effective psychological and pedagogical approaches. These approaches should be aimed at adapting teaching and upbringing methods to modern requirements. Of particular importance is the issue of introducing effective methods of independent work into the educational process. The ability to work independently contributes to the formation of students' desire to be self-confident, independent, educated and creative in thinking. Currently, such qualities are becoming in demand.

The organization of independent work and its management is a responsible and difficult task for every teacher. The transfer of knowledge, skills, beliefs and spirituality is not limited to words from teacher to student. This process includes familiarization with the material, its perception, independent development, awareness and acceptance of skills and concepts. One of the most important functions of independent work is the formation of a highly cultured personality, since it is in the process of independent intellectual and spiritual activity that a person develops.

Organizing and conducting independent work is one of the ways to stimulate students' active learning activities. Currently, they occupy an important place in the lesson, since it is in the process of independent work that students acquire knowledge. Under the guidance of a teacher, students should actively work in the classroom. Passive listening to the

material or memorizing it from a textbook is not sufficient for the assimilation of knowledge. Only what is learned through active self-labor is firmly and reliably fixed.

Independent work forces and subsequently teaches the student to look for answers to questions, explore additional literature, highlight the main and essential, give explanations and interpretations of natural phenomena, as well as develop critical thinking skills, formulate hypotheses and conduct research. Ultimately, independent work allows students to actively acquire knowledge.

Independent work is an essential and integral part of any lesson, since it eliminates aimless pastime, activates thinking and provides a stronger and deeper assimilation of educational material. It is important that independent work be diverse and their duration correspond to the characteristics of a particular class.

And K.D. Ushinsky said very well about this: "... the child demands activity incessantly and gets tired not of activity, but of its monotony and one-sidedness."

Independent study refers to any organized activity of students aimed at achieving a certain educational goal at a certain time. This includes the search for knowledge, its comprehension, consolidation, development of skills and abilities, as well as generalization and systematization of acquired knowledge. Experts in the field of education emphasize the importance of providing students with methods and tools for self-organization of the learning process. This means that it is necessary to equip them with the skills and abilities of planning academic work, the ability to set goals and choose the appropriate means to achieve them.

To form a complex and balanced personality, it is necessary to regularly include it in independent activities, especially in the form of specially organized educational tasks, such as independent work, which stimulate problem-seeking activity. One of the key requirements of modern society for the educational system is the formation of a personality capable of independent and creative solution of scientific, industrial and social tasks, critical thinking, protection of one's point of view and beliefs. It is also important

that she systematically and continuously replenish and update her knowledge through self-education, develop skills and abilities, and then successfully apply them in practice.

To achieve these goals, we can identify the following requirements for the organization of independent work of students:

1. Each independent work in the lesson should have a clear goal, and the student should be familiar with the methods of achieving it.
2. Independent work should be adapted to the student's learning abilities. The transition from one level of difficulty to another should be carried out gradually.
3. The teacher must provide a variety of forms of independent work and control the process of completing tasks.
4. Independent work should be as free from patterns as possible, since its main purpose is to stimulate the development of cognitive abilities, initiative and creative thinking of the student.

During the educational process, various forms of independent work of students are used. These forms can be classified according to various criteria: by didactic purpose, by the nature of students' educational activities, by content, by the degree of independence and the level of creativity of students.

From the point of view of the didactic purpose, independent work can be divided into five categories:

- obtaining new knowledge and developing the skill of self-acquisition of knowledge.
- consolidation and clarification of existing knowledge.
- formation of the ability to apply knowledge in solving educational and practical tasks.
- development of practical skills and abilities.
- stimulating creative thinking and the ability to apply knowledge in difficult situations.

Study assignments for independent work, in turn, can be divided into:

1. According to the method of independent work of students:

* observation;

* exercise;

* working with the text of the textbook

2. According to the links of the educational process

* perception task

*the task of systematization

* assignment to consolidate the educational material

* the task of repeating the educational material

3. By the nature of the cognitive activity of the student

*Reproductive tasks

Creative (productive)

4. By the nature of the leadership

*Detailed instructions

* less detailed instructions.

In practice, the following types of independent work can be distinguished:

Working with a book: drawing, graph, searching for an answer to a question, taking notes, retelling, an answer plan, summarizing in several paragraphs, working with primary sources.

When planning each topic of the curriculum, it is important to determine beforehand what knowledge and observations from life will be required to master it. This includes familiarization with the requirements of the program, studying the contents of the textbook and additional literature, as well as determining the facilities for conducting excursions, the timing of practical classes and observation topics for students. When preparing for

lessons, it is important to think in advance about all the methods by which you can stimulate curiosity and activate the cognitive abilities of students.

When planning independent work, it is necessary:

- take into account its place in the overall structure of the lesson.
- determine the optimal amount of work, taking into account the level of preparedness of students and the complexity of the material being studied.
- Take into account the possible difficulties that students may face when completing assignments.
- choose the appropriate form of tasks.
- set the optimal working time.
- select the appropriate training material.
- provide effective methods of checking and self-monitoring of students' completed work.

There are some structural principles that allow you to analyze the meaning, place and functions of independent activity. There are two approaches that, although similar in nature, have different content and specifics. When combining these approaches, the essence of independent activity is determined.

The first group:

- content component: includes knowledge that is expressed through concepts, images, perceptions and representations.
- Operational component: covers various actions, skills and techniques, both externally and internally.
- productive component: includes new knowledge, ways of acting, social experience, ideas, abilities and qualities that are the result of independent activity.

The second group:

- content component: includes the allocation of a cognitive task and the definition of the goals of educational activity.
- procedural component: includes the selection, definition and application of appropriate methods of action aimed at achieving the set goals.
- motivational component: includes the need for new knowledge, which serves as a source of motivation for performing actions and realizing the meaning of educational activities.

The actual process of independent activity is presented in the form of a triad: motive – action – result.

Thus, it can be concluded that independent work is not just a form of organizing training sessions or a method of teaching. It can be considered as a means of stimulating students to independent cognitive activity and a means of logical and psychological organization of this activity.

Literature

1. Gornostaev Z.Ya. "The problem of independent cognitive activity" //Is open.school. – 1998. - No.2
- Russian Russian language lessons //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2024. – Vol. 3. – No. 1. – pp. 77-81.
3. Ergasheva D. K., Istamov D. The concept of "mother" in the conceptual sphere of the Russian people on the material of proverbs and sayings //research and education. – 2022. – Vol. 1. – No. 9. – pp. 423-427.
4. Ergasheva D. K. The Concept of "Mother Image" in Russian Proverbs and Sayings //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2022. – Vol. 28. – pp. 224-226.
5. Ubaydova D. A. Ergasheva D. K. The history of the creation of lexicographic dictionaries, theoretical and practical ways of development //European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability. – 2021. – Vol. 2. – No. 3. – pp. 29-32.

6. Ergasheva D. K. The image of women and men in proverbs and sayings of the Russian people //Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal. – 2022. – Vol. 1. – No. 2. – pp. 203-210.